

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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ISSUES OF STRATEGIC PLANNING IN INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES

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Abstract: This article examines strategic planning, its organization, development, and localization of production using modern strategies in large industrial enterprises. It focuses on supporting and economically regulating production, improving efficiency, analyzing factors influencing organizational management, and providing scientific-practical proposals and recommendations for enhancement.

Key words: organizations, strategy, strategic planning, production, localization, modern methods, technology, export, management, efficient use, production development, diversified strategies.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada sanoat korxonalarida strategik rejalashtirish, uni tashkil etish, zamonaviy strategiyalardan foydalanish orqali ishlab chiqarishni rivojlantirish hamda mahalliyashtirish, uni qo'llab-quvvatlash, iqtisodiy tartibga solish va ularning samaradorligini oshirish masalalari ko'rib chiqilgan. Shuningdek, tashkilot boshqaruviga ta'sir etuvchi omillarni o'rganish, baholash va uni takomillashtirish yuzasidan ilmiy-amaliy taklif va tavsiyalar ishlab chiqilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: tashkilotlar, strategiya, strategik rejalashtirish, ishlab chiqarish, mahalliyashtirish, zamonaviy usullar, texnologiya, eksport, boshqaruv, samarali foydalanish, ishlab chiqarishni rivojlantirish, diversifikatsiyalangan strategiyalar.

Аннотация: В статье рассмотрено стратегическое планирование, его организация, развитие и локализация производства посредством использования современных стратегий на крупных производственных предприятиях. Исследованы вопросы поддержки, экономического регулирования, повышения эффективности, факторы влияющие на организационное управление, даны оценка, научно-практические предложения и рекомендации по совершенствованию управления.

Ключевые слова: организация, стратегия, стратегическое планирование, производство, локализация, современные методы, технологии, экспорт, менеджмент, эффективное использование, развитие производства, диверсифицированные стратегии.

INTRODUCTION

Strategic planning is a process of carefully and thoughtfully aligning the strengths of a company's business with the opportunities available in its chosen business environment. While strategic planning is both a science and an art, it is generally believed that for the planning process to be consistently effective, managers must gather, screen, and analyze information about the company's business environment. They must identify and evaluate the company's strengths and weaknesses and develop a clear mission for the company, along with achievable goals and objectives, which then serve as the foundation for tactical and operational plans. Strategic planning is an essential process for every company, regardless of the size of its business and the time and other resources available for developing, documenting, implementing, and monitoring the strategic plan. The business environment and relevant technologies are constantly evolving, and new risks and uncertainties will regularly emerge.

The widely accepted theory of corporate strategic planning is simple: using a time horizon of several years, top management reassesses its current strategy by looking for opportunities and threats in the environment and by analyzing the company's resources to identify its strengths and weaknesses. Management may develop

several alternative strategic scenarios and evaluate them against the long-term objectives of the organization. To begin implementing the chosen strategy (or continue with a revalidated one), management details the actions to be taken in the near future.

In smaller companies, strategic planning is a less formal, almost continuous process. The president and his small group of managers meet frequently to resolve strategic issues and outline their next steps. They do not require an elaborate, formalized planning system. Even in relatively large, undiversified corporations, the functional structure allows executives to evaluate strategic alternatives and their implications on an ad hoc basis. The number of key executives involved in such decisions is typically small, and they are located close enough for frequent, informal meetings.

However, large, diversified corporations present a different environment for planning. Most of them use a product/market division organizational structure that allows decentralized decision-making involving many responsibility-center managers. Since many managers must be involved in decisions requiring coordinated action, informal planning is almost impossible.

Our focus in this research is on formal planning processes in complex organizations. However, the thought processes behind undertaking planning, as described in the opening paragraph, are fundamentally the same regardless of the organization's size. Therefore, even executives in smaller corporate settings that rely on informal planning can benefit from the structured process outlined here, as it helps clarify their thinking. Formalizing the steps in the process involves explaining the purpose and value of each step.

Every corporate executive frequently uses the terms "strategy" and "planning" when addressing the most critical aspects of their role. For the president, strategy is a primary concern, with strategic planning being central to their responsibilities. A division general manager often considers themselves akin to the president of their division, taking ownership of its strategy and ensuring that the strategic planning supports its vitality and growth. Similarly, executives responsible for functional areas, such as a division marketing manager, understand the importance of strategic planning. After all, strategies related to marketing, manufacturing, or research are pivotal to the company's overall success.

LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE TOPIC

The theoretical and practical significance of the research results lies in the fact that the developed scientific conclusions and practical recommendations can be applied in the implementation of strategic planning for the effective management of manufacturing enterprises. The dissertation can be utilized by undergraduate students majoring in management for course and graduate work, as well as in the discipline "Strategic Management."

A group of foreign scholars, including A. Chandler, D. Faulkner, G. Johnson, J. Kay, M. Armstrong, R. Rumelt, H. Frizevinkel, J.A. Piersa, R.B. Robinson, R.V. Rue, P.G. Golland, I. Ansoff, R. Cartwright, G. Mintzberg, U. Nyuman, K. Andrews, D. Shendel, K. Hatten, Y. Schumpeter, A. Koul, G. Simon, J. March, Ch. Lindblom, R. Kayert, K. Veyk, J. Quinn, K. Praxalad, G. Xemel, G. Allison, J. Pfeffer, G. Estli, E. Renman, R. Normann, D. Pyu, D. Campbell, D. Stonexaus, B. Houston, Kim U. Chan, and R. Moborns have made significant contributions to the scientific approaches to strategic management [4].

Theoretical and methodological foundations of strategic management have been developed by scholars from the CIS countries, including M.I. Sokolova, L.G. Zeitsev, G. Kerntsner, Yu.A. Malenkov, A.M. Popovich, D.A. Aaker, Yu.V. Babanova, O.S. Viksanskiy, I.B. Gurkov, A.V. Kurlykova, A.V. Aleksandrova, S.A. Kurashova, N.B. Akatov, A.V. Andreychikov, L.E. Basovskiy, Yu.V. Guskov, and A.T. Zublar [7].

In Uzbekistan, the above issues have been addressed in the scientific works of N.K. Yuldashev, B.Yu. Khodiev, M.A. Ikramov, A.H. Kuchkarov, E. Koldoshev, and others [3].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research methodology includes the use of observation, generalization, dynamic comparison, logical analysis, and comparative methods.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In Namangan region, several measures are being taken to enhance media engagement, maintain a website, and provide information to entrepreneurs through electronic means. Since the beginning of the year, the regional department has been publishing articles and announcements in various media outlets. The website has covered a total of 76 news items since the start of the year. We will continue our analysis using the data in the table below.

Table-1. Information on speeches made in the media.

№	The media	Total number of published materials
1	Print media	4
2	TV	6
3	Advertising	0
4	Radio	0
5	Web resource	76
6	Web resource in telegram	225
7	Web resource users	843

Source: "Author's development based on the data of the Namangan regional department of the Chamber of

Commerce and Industry of Uzbekistan.

As a result of the research, the factors that negatively affect the formation and development of effective management strategies in business activities were studied.

Table-2. Major problems in the business environment.

№	Problems	% Of total respondents
1	High credit rate	80
2	High taxes	72
3	Non-transparency and bureaucratic tender processes	46
4	Access to tender information	42
5	Execution of permits	39
6	Access to information on technology and equipment	36
7	Problems with regulatory authorities	36
8	Problems of product certification	31
9	Licensing issues	30
10	Obstruction of fair competition by the shadow (secret) business	26

Source: Author's development based on research sources.

In addition, each sector of the department has organized a total of 5 telegram "Bots", which provide daily news, information on the conditions created for entrepreneurs and various benefits provided by the state.

According to the table above, the presence of problems such as high credit rates, high taxes, non-transparency and bureaucratic tender processes has been repeatedly mentioned by entrepreneurs.

Entrepreneurs also pointed out the *existence of problems with regulators, product certification, licensing, and obstruction of fair competition by the shadow (secret) business.*

We describe the percentages of the problems using the following diagram.

Figure-1. Major problems in the business environment.

In addition to these problems, some infrastructure problems can be seen in business activities - access to land, access to vacant buildings and structures, ARV (architectural and planning functions), gas and energy supply, sewerage, heating, water supply, telephone, etc.

Entrepreneurs pointed out the main infrastructure problems in their activities - access to land plots, access to vacant buildings and structures, ARV (architectural and planning functions), gas supply, energy supply, sewerage, heating, water supply and telephone communication. Hence, these infrastructure problems also indicate that certain strategies in the field are not being used properly or that optimal strategies have not been developed.

Research has also shown that there are the following factors that negatively affect the development of entrepreneurship:

- in terms of regulation, issues of tax system regulation and banking system regulation, as well as cases of neglect of existing problems by local authorities;
- the main barriers to attracting foreign investment are staffing issues, lack of information for investors, as well as low levels of interest from local authorities.

The process of strategy formulation can be conceptualized as occurring at three organizational levels, as illustrated in Exhibit I: headquarters (corporate strategy), division (business strategy), and department (functional strategy). The planning processes leading to the formulation of these strategies are often referred to in parallel as corporate planning, business planning, and functional planning. To construct the framework of the planning process, we must first briefly define these notations:

Corporate Planning and Strategy – Corporate objectives are set at the highest organizational levels. Corporate planning, which leads to the formulation of corporate strategy, is the process of:

- (a) deciding on the company's overall objectives and goals, including determining the number and type of business lines to pursue,
- (b) acquiring the necessary resources to achieve these objectives, and
- (c) allocating resources across various business units to ensure the objectives are met. (For further clarification, see the sidebar on "Objectives and Goals" for definitions of these terms as used in this article.)

Business Planning and Strategy – Business planning, which results in the formulation of business strategy, is the process of defining the scope of a division's activities to satisfy a broad consumer need. This includes setting division-specific objectives, establishing policies to meet those objectives, and determining the strategic direction of the division. Strategy formulation in this context involves selecting the division's objectives and goals, as well as defining its operational scope with regard to markets, geographical areas, and/or technology.

Thus, while business planning focuses on a homogeneous set of activities within a division, corporate planning takes a broader view, addressing the portfolio of all business divisions. Corporate planning evaluates proposed changes in one division in terms of how they impact the overall composition of the entire portfolio.

Functional Planning and Strategy – In functional planning, departments create feasible action programs to implement the division's strategy. The division, based on its objectives, selects the subset of these programs to execute and coordinates the action plans of the various functional departments. Strategy formulation at this level involves setting objectives and goals for each functional area (such as marketing, production, finance, research, etc.), and determining the sequence of actions required for each area to meet its goals. These programs become the foundational components of the strategic functional plans.

It is important to note that these levels of strategy are interrelated, influencing each other to varying degrees.

To further assess the formation and development of management strategies in American corporations, we will now conduct a SWOT analysis.

Table-3. Evaluate the national strategic system for corporations in the United States.

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - strong methodological base; - effective operation of the feedback mechanism; - strong forecasting system; - strengthening the strategy in the short term; - strategy management at the industrial level; - Grant management of regional development strategy; - linking budget planning with indicators for evaluating the implementation of targeted programs; - system flexibility, rapid response to external changes; - rich human resources 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - high flow of management staff; "death" of startups in American business since 2008; - huge foreign debt; - Bankruptcy of some states, districts, cities and regions
Opportunity	Danger
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - technological superiority in the development of artificial intelligence; - Further expansion and growth of American multinational corporations; - Strengthening the leadership role of the United States in world politics. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - economic competition with the European Union and China; - growing problems in the field of education; - growing problems in the national health system; - growing crime; - Increasing the number of homeless and unemployed people
Total score: 3	

Summarizing the data in the table, it has 3 points in the formation and development of management strategies in U.S.A. corporations.

Like their foreign counterparts, the 60-hour workweek is the norm for American leaders who work hard. Most of them also work 90 hours a week.

Intensive work regimen requires physical training and good health. No matter how busy the work day is, most managers manage to find time for physical education classes. However, the American governance model should not be idealized. because fierce competition in the labor market requires maximum efficiency and responsibility from every employee.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Today, the European Union, which unites 27 countries, was formed in the 1950 y. The process of expanding it is ongoing, but there are also cases of dissatisfaction with the single policy and economic problems¹. EU to Finland, Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland, Czech Republic, Slovakia, Hungary, Romania, Bulgaria, Croatia, Slovenia, Netherlands, Cyprus, Bulgaria, Sweden, Denmark, Ireland, Germany, Austria, Belgium, Luxembourg, France, These include Spain, Portugal and Greece. In 2021, the UK left the European Union. Of these, we describe the process of developing and shaping the governance strategy of the German state. The positive results achieved by the German economy show the effectiveness of the organizational and management system. In Germany, the main goals of management are to maximize profits and ensure the payment of dividends to shareholders. In addition, German leaders:

- to ensure a leading position of their companies in the market;
- development of production through permanent investment;

¹ <https://visasam.ru/emigration/vybor/spisok-stran-evrosojuza.html>.

- Active research and development;
- solving environmental problems;
- strive to carry out training and education.

The sum of the recommended division goals is likely to be inadequate to achieve the goals envisioned by headquarters for the entire organization. In trying to close this “planning gap,” corporate management has only three choices:

1. It can improve division performance by pressing, during the review of division recommendations, for more aggressive strategies and more ambitious goals.
2. It can divert company resources into more promising businesses. This move may give rise to an acquisition program.
3. It can decide that the corporate goals are unrealistic and scale them down.

The fact that the corporation’s goals normally are more or less the sum of those division goals sought by top management implies that headquarters is concerned with rather minor adjustments of this portfolio of goals. If so, the first cycle of formal planning has the salutary effect of providing an annual “mid-course correction” to the trajectory of the combined businesses. Momentum is a factor in the continued success of a diversified corporation—as with a rocket headed for the moon—and a wise chief executive does not dissipate it needlessly. Rather, he nudges the bundle of energies represented by his division managers, trying to make minor adjustments early enough to be nondisruptive and at the same time affect the corporation’s position several years ahead.

Yet there is little doubt that formalizing the planning process is worthwhile; it ensures that managers at all levels will devote some time to strategic thinking, and it guarantees each of them an audience for his ideas. While formal strategic planning cannot guarantee good ideas, it can increase the odds sufficiently to yield a handsome payoff.

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